

DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS APPLICATIONS IN THE STUDY OF A GEOLOGICAL INDICATOR

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ABSTRACT. The differences between shallow neural networks and deep neural networks are considered. Data from operational exploration of an open pit mine are used to train different types of deep neural networks to predict a useful indicator. The results of deep network training are compared both with each other and with previous results obtained from the training of shallow neural networks. The errors in training and testing of the models according to the number of layers and nodes in the networks are analysed.

Key words: deep neural networks, deep learning

Introduction and previous work

In the recent years, artificial neural networks have become one of the preferred tools in data mining (Han et.al, 2011). They are used both in data classification and for modelling and forecasting data (regression analysis). For the past 20 years, researchers at the University of Mining and Geology have been studying the ability of neural networks to analyse data from the mining industry. Topalov and Hristov (2007) examined the possibility and the quality of modelling by neural networks of geological parameters of ore deposit. Data from the operational study of individual horizons in an open pit mine were used. In another work (Topalov, Hristov, 2008) the possibility of predicting a quality indicator in one horizon of an open pit mine with a trained neural network on the data from several previous horizons is evaluated. Further (Hristov, Topalov, 2011) the influence of the sample density on the quality of training of the neural network is studied. The same authors (Hristov, Topalov, 2012) investigated the possibility for application of neural networks in forecasting the extraction in an underground mine. Hristov (2015) and Hristov and Topalov (2015) considered other aspects of such research on mining data.

Some years ago, according to the number of hidden layers, neural networks were divided into single-layer and multilayer ones. Recently, single-layer nets are called shallow, while multilayer networks are referred to as deep networks. In addition, the research on deep neural networks is named deep learning.

The aim of the present study is to determine how the number of hidden layers and the number of neurons in them affect the quality of the analysis of data from ore exploration.

Experimental Framework

The dataset was obtained from the operational study of mining horizon 1015 from the open pit "Ellatsite". The data includes 1954 instances with the following parameters - coordinates (x, y) of the sample and content of useful indicator copper (Cu).

For the study, a neural network simulator Neural Designer by Artelnic is used.

The experiment is divided into two parts. Firstly, the influence on the quality of the analysis of the number of hidden layers of the neural network is sought.

Once this number of layers has been determined, the second study looked at the effect on quality by changing the number of neurons in the hidden layers.

A regression neural network of Perceptron type is used. The architecture contains two input neurons for the coordinates (x, y) of the instances in the first (input layer), a various number of hidden layers and one neuron for the copper content in the output layer (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Neural network architecture: deep neural network (a) and shallow neural network (b)

The data is divided into three sets: 1174 instances for the training set, 390 instances for the validation set, and 390 instances for the test set (after training). The quasi-Newton method is used here as a training algorithm. Neuron activation function is a hyperbolic tangent. Training stopping criterion is reaching 1000 epochs (iterations) or training maximum time of 1 hour, or 100 epochs without training error decrease. In the first study, the number of neurons in the hidden layers of the network is fixed at 20. The following networks are examined: a shallow network - 20 neurons in the hidden layer, a two-layer network with 10x10 neurons, a three-layer network - 7x7x6 neurons, a four-layer network - 5x5x5x5, a five-layer network - 4x4x4x4x4 and a twenty-layer network - 20 layers with one neuron in each layer.

Based on the results of the first part, and after the optimal number of layers was found, the second study experimented with networks of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 neurons in each hidden layer.

Results and discussion

The mean value of the useful Cu index in the tested instances is 0.076 and the variance is 0.031. The distribution of Cu is given in Figure 2 and as can be seen it is normal.

Fig. 2. Cu distribution

The results of the training and the testing of the neural networks from the first study are presented in Table 1. The correlation coefficients were calculated as a ratio between the actual Cu content in the instances and the predicted Cu content calculated by the neural networks. From Figure 3 it is seen that the two-layer network's correlation provides the best outcome, i.e. the conclusion from the first study is that, with a fixed number of neurons (20), the deep neural network with two hidden layers achieves best quality in modelling and forecasting the discussed geological indicator (Figure 4).

Table 1. First experiment results

Number of hidden layers	Training mean squared error	Testing mean squared error	Correlation
1	0.00033	0.00040	0.562
2	0.00030	0.00033	0.822
3	0.00030	0.00035	0.81
4	0.00028	0.00040	0.785
5	0.00027	0.00041	0.784
20	0.00107	0.00101	0.00

Based on the first experiment results, second study was performed on deep neural networks with two hidden layers. Networks with 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 neurons in each hidden layer were trained. The results are shown in Table 2. The correlations show that the neural network with 10 neurons in a layer gives the most accurate results. On the other hand, the observed deviations between testing and training errors show that networks with 10 and 12 neurons are prone to be overtraining.

The differences in the correlation coefficients of networks with 4 neurons or more per layer are very close.

Fig. 3. Correlation coefficients according to the number of hidden layers of the trained neural networks

Fig.4. Linear regression of the dependency between actual and predicted Cu contents in a deep neural network with two hidden layers

Therefore, a two-layer network with 4x4 neurons in the hidden layers can be used with the same quality, and it has the simplest architecture (number of neurons and number of connections between them).

Table 2. Second experiment results

Number of neurons	Training mean squared error	Testing mean squared error	Correlation
2	0.00060	0.00058	0.587
4	0.00034	0.00029	0.821
6	0.00032	0.00032	0.8
8	0.00030	0.00031	0.81
10	0.00030	0.00033	0.822
12	0.00028	0.00031	0.806

Conclusion

Based on the performed research by comparing deep learning with shallow learning techniques, it can be concluded that the deep neural network with two hidden layers delivers superior quality results compared to the other used neural

networks with various depths (in terms of number of hidden layers).

By varying with the number of the neurons in the two-layer deep network, it is observed that the network with 4 neurons per layer gives the most balanced results: correlation with higher accuracy, lack of overtraining and a simplified structure.

As a main conclusion of the study, it can be assumed that based on the same characteristics, deep neural networks give slightly better results than shallow ones.

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